

Original Article/Review Article/etc

Manuscript Template: Preparation of Manuscript for JPUB Journals

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Received: 01.01.2021

• Accepted: 01.01.2021

• Published: 01.01.2021

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Keywords: Enter up to five keywords and separate them by commas

1. Introduction

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1.1. Sections and subsections

Articles should be divided into sections and subsections. Principal sections should be numbered consecutively (e.g., as 1. Introduction, 2. Materials and methods, etc.), while subsections should be numbered as 1.1., 1.2., etc. Do not use numbers for the Acknowledgments and References sections. The total number of pages for the abstract, all sections (e.g., Introduction, Materials and methods, Results, Discussion, etc.), references, tables, and figures should not exceed 15. For this journal, one of the most common return reason during initial submissions is exceeding the number of pages. The number of pages is strictly limited; because, this journal is free of charge (for both authors and readers).

The Introduction should argue the case for the study, outlining only essential include background, and should not include details of findings or conclusions. It should not be only a review of the subject area, but it should also contain a clear statement of the question being addressed. In the Materials and methods section, please provide concise but complete information on materials and analytical/statistical procedures used. This part should be as clear as possible to enable other scientists to repeat the research presented. For example, brand names and company locations should be supplied for all mentioned equipment, instruments, chemicals, etc. Results of the study should be given in the Results section. In the Discussion section, where findings are discussed, statements from the Introduction and Results sections should not be repeated unnecessarily. It is advised that the final paragraph of the Discussion section highlights the main conclusions of the study. The Results and Discussion sections may be combined. Where necessary, you can refer to sections like Section 1.

Manuscripts must be written in English. Contributors who are not native English speakers are strongly advised to ensure that a colleague fluent in the English language or a professional language editor has reviewed their manuscript. Concise English without jargon should be used. Repetitive use of long sentences and passive voices should be avoided. It is strongly recommended that the text be run through computer spelling and grammar programs. Either British or American spelling is acceptable but it must be consistent throughout. Manuscripts written in poor English will not be submitted to referees for evaluation and will be returned back to authors.

Please note that the first paragraph of a section or subsection is not indented. The first paragraphs that follows a table, figure, equation etc. does not have an indent, either. Subsequent paragraphs, however, are indented.

Sample Heading (Third Level). Only two levels of headings should be numbered. Lower level headings remain unnumbered; they are formatted as run-in headings.

Sample Heading (Forth Level). The contribution should contain no more than four levels of headings. The following Table 1 gives a summary of all heading levels.

Table 1. Table captions should be placed above the tables.

Heading level	Example	Font size and style
Title	Manuscripts title	18 point, bold
1 st -level heading	1 Introduction	13 point, bold
2 nd -level heading	2.1 Printing Area	11 point, bold
3 rd -level heading	Run-in Heading in Bold. Text follows	11 point, bold
4 th -level heading	<i>Lowest Level Heading.</i> Text follows	11 point, italic

Detailed instructions for preparing the manuscript are listed in section 2. Manuscript Preparation. When you prepare the manuscript, you can follow the descriptive rules presented in sub-section Descriptive rules.

2. Manuscript Preparation

2.1. Descriptive rules

Paper Size

The paper must use a page size corresponding to A4, which is 21 x 29.7 cm. Only this paper size can be accepted. The margins must be set as follows:

- Top = 2.45 cm
- Bottom = 2.45 cm
- Left = Right = 2.6 cm

Fonts

Use Roman typeface (e.g. Times, Times New Roman) throughout the paper. Font sizes and styles to be used in the paper are summarized in Table 3.

Tables

Insert tables where appropriate (as close as possible to where they are mentioned in the text). Prefer positioning them at the top or at the bottom of the page. If necessary, span them over the page. Enumerate them consecutively using Arabic numbers and provide a caption for each table (e.g. Table 1, Table 2,..), unless there is only one table, in which case it should be labelled "Table" without numbering. Captions must be written in sentence case (e.g., "Macroscopic appearance of the samples."). The font used inside the figures should be Times New Roman. Use font 9 regular for table caption and table legend. Place table captions and table legend above the table. Leave one blank line before (15 point) and one after (5 point) the captions.

Table 2. Table caption

Table legend

Table data

Figures

Insert figures where appropriate (as close as possible to where they are mentioned in the text). Prefer positioning them at the top or at the bottom of the column. If necessary, span them over both columns. Enumerate them consecutively using Arabic numbers and provide a caption for each figure (e.g. Figure 1, Figure 2,..). Use font 8 regular for figure caption and figure legend. Place figure legend beneath figures. Leave one blank line before (5 point) and one after (15 point) the captions. Please keep in mind the distinction between tables and figures: tables only contain alphanumerical characters and no graphical elements. Do not use characters smaller than 9 points within figures. Figures are going to be reproduced in color in the electronic versions of the Proceedings, but when choosing graph colors, keep in mind that they might be printed in black and white color. Figure 1 is intended to illustrate the positioning of a figure.

All figures and tables must be numbered consecutively as they are referred to in the text. Please refer to tables and figures with capitalization and as unabbreviated (e.g., "As shown in Figure 2...", and not "Fig. 2" or "figure 2").

Figure 1. A figure caption is always placed below the illustration.

Table 3. Font sizes and styles

Item	Font Size	Font Style
Title	18	Bold
Author	12	Bold
Authors' info	11	Italic
Abstract	11	Regular
Keywords	11	Regular
Body text	11	Regular
Table caption	9	Regular
Table legend	9	Regular
Column titles	9	Regular
Table data	9	Regular
Figure caption	9	Regular
Figure legend	9	Regular
Acknowledgment	11	Regular
References	10	Regular

Equations

For inserting equations, use the Equation Editor. Enumerate the equations using Arabic numbers in brackets on the right hand side of the equation. Equations are centered and set on a separate line.

$$x + y = z \tag{1}$$

Then, it can be referred in the text as (1).

Reference citations

References should be cited in the text by numbers in square brackets. Please do not use individual sets of square brackets for citation numbers that appear together, e.g., use [1, 4] or [1-3, 5], not

[1],[2],[3], or [4]-[6]. All references cited in the manuscript must appear in the list of references at the end, while all references listed in the reference list must be cited in the manuscript.

Itemizing

In case you need to itemize parts of your text, use either bullets or numbers.

3. Information about references

Do not include personal communications, unpublished data, websites, or other unpublished materials as references, although such material may be inserted (in parentheses) in the text. If the author of a reference is an organization or corporation, use its name in the reference list (using an abbreviation in the citation, if appropriate); do not use "Anonymous".

All authors should be included in reference lists unless there are 6 or more, in which case only the first 5 should be given, followed by "et al.". The manuscript should be checked carefully to ensure that the spellings of the authors' names and the years are exactly the same in the text as given in the reference list. References should be formatted as shown at the end of this document. Journal titles should be abbreviated according to Thomson Reuters Web of Science © abbreviations.

Acknowledgment

Acknowledgment and/or disclaimers should appear before References. Names of funding organizations should be written in full. The authors are advised to describe author contributions, e.g., as follows: S.A. gave the idea, F.A. did the experiments, F.A. and S.A. interpreted the results, S.A. wrote the paper.

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